

CONTROL OF COMPENSATORY MECHANISMS OF UPPER EXTREMITY STRENGTH ABILITIES IN PRESCHOOL AGE

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Abstract

Objective: The main goal of this study is to assess the ability to accurately reproduce muscle effort and the ability to internally readjust compensatory mechanisms depending on the objectively existing functional relationship between kinematics and the muscle force field. **Methods:** Following the cluster analysis made in the theoretical part, experiments were also conducted on the accuracy of reproducing a given muscle effort. For the purpose of the experiments, it turned out to be necessary to construct a specialized strain gauge sensor for measuring the readings in manual dynamometry. According to this preliminary experience, the motor task required its repetition without the participation of the visual analyzer. **Results:** The results of the handgrip strength test showed that this test is not reliable in all age groups, the correlation coefficients remained below the level of 0.8. It is particularly interesting that in older age groups a significant correlation higher than 0.9 with the data from the hand dynamometry was observed. **Conclusion:** The conclusions from the development point to the idea of rethinking the methods and tools for assessing the ability to accurately reproduce muscular effort and the ability to internally readjust compensatory mechanisms.

Keywords: Motor control, dynamometry, compensatory mechanisms, preschool age

Introduction

Upper limb strength is an important element of an individual's overall physical fitness, and it is no coincidence that every motor skills test battery also includes a test for assessing upper limb strength [1, 2, 3]. A certain wave-like rhythm is also observed in growth. The regularities in the development of all systems of the organism have been established and data was published [4, 5, 6]. The development of different muscle groups proceeds unevenly and individually [7]. Each has a specific ontogenetic development. For example, the muscular system of a child still constitutes only 27% of the body weight, while in an adult it is 42%, with large muscle groups developing earlier than small ones [8, 9]. There are also certain regularities in the development of the ratio between the trunk and the limbs [10]. Force is defined as the ability of a person to overcome and counteract external resistance at the expense of muscular effort [11]. The magnitude of muscular strength depends on the following factors: neuromuscular, anatomical-physiological, biochemical, etc. [12].

A number of authors define a person's strength abilities as fundamental for the manifestation of the individual's other motor abilities - speed-force, strength endurance, agility and flexibility [13].

The analysis of various literary sources leads us to the idea that both development and upbringing have their role in the formation of motor skills. Therefore, taking into account the stages in the development of individual subsystems in the motor apparatus, the optimization of educational work should be sought on the basis of the undoubtedly existing connection between development and upbringing. This idea should be tested through a suitably constructed pedagogical experiment. In other words, we could expect that for each age group there is an optimum of biomechanical characteristics (far from all) that should be improved in the educational process.

METHODS

The main objective of this study is to assess the ability to accurately reproduce muscle effort and the ability to internally readjust compensatory mechanisms depending on the objectively existing functional relationship between kinematics and the muscle force field.

Following the cluster analysis performed in the theoretical part, experiments were conducted to determine the accuracy of reproducing a given muscle effort. For the purpose of the experiments, it was necessary to construct a specialized strain gauge sensor for measuring the readings in manual dynamometry. The effort = $\frac{1}{2}F_{max}$. was programmatically visualized on the computer screen during an additional attempt. According to this preliminary experiment, the motor task required its repetition without the participation of the visual analyzer. In addition, the test was repeated in wrist flexion (135°) to assess the ability to control compensatory mechanisms during prior contraction of the agonist muscles.

This experiment was repeated with a change in the length of the agonist muscle (flexion in the wrist joint at 20°) and a change in the angular ratio of the uninvolved degree of freedom (adduction in the shoulder joint – sideways at 90°). The entire battery of tests was experimented on a limited number of experienced individuals (ten people each) for each age group.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the results of the manual dynamometry test for boys and girls in total. The data show a tendency towards a worsening of asymmetry with increasing age. The large individual differences are striking. There are children with prolonged preservation of complete symmetry and those in whom the asymmetry is higher than 100%.

Table 1.

Data from the manual dynamometry test

years	Hand dynamometry					
	boys			girls		
	x%	S	v%	x%	S	v%
3	4,41	1,8	40,81	4,01	1,4	34,91
4	4,82	1,8	37,34	4,41	1,6	36,28
5	5,21	2	38,38	4,62	2,1	45,45
6	6,44	2,4	37,26	5,34	2,3	43,07
7	7,68	2,8	36,45	5,64	2,7	47,87

Furthermore, up to the age of 6, no statistically significant difference was found between boys and girls, and at the age of 7, the reliability was higher than 90%, according to Student's t-test. The extremely high values of the variance estimates could be due to both genotypic and phenotypic factors.

Something that we believe is essential is the discrediting of the results of the experiment for assessing the "static force". The results showed that this test is not reliable in all age groups, the correlation coefficients remained below the level of 0.8. A particularly interesting fact is that in the older age groups a significant correlation higher than 0.9 with the data from the manual dynamometry is observed. This may be due both to the fact that the same parameter is measured and to the involvement of the smaller muscle groups of the grip on the outcome of the dynamometry.

To this end, we conducted an additional experiment on a limited number of experienced individuals using a fixed externally provided grip. The results led to a statistically proven trend for increasing the registered strength. Therefore, in these age groups, any future experiments to assess grip strength should be carried out with additional aids to ensure grip. We refrained from such experiments due to the establishment of some indications of possible injuries in the lumbar region.

Figures 1–4 graphically illustrate the trend in the development of this type of management with age. The extremely large errors in younger ages are striking, as, unlike physical qualities, a certain decrease in the slope of the approximating line is noticeable in the period between 4 and 5 years.

Figure 1. Comfortable hand Grip – Boys

Figure 2. Comfortable hand Grip – Girls

Figure 3. Folded grip – boys

Figure 4. Folded grip - girls

Table 2 presents data on the average values of standard deviations and coefficients of variation from this type of experiments.

Table 2.

Data on the average values of standard deviations and coefficients of variation

years old	Indicator	3 years			4 years			5 years			6 years			7 years			
		x%	S	V	x%	S	V	x%	S	V	x%	S	V	x%	S	V	
	Grip comfortable hand	b	21	6.1	29.05	18	4.4	24.44	16	4.1	25.625	8	2.2	27.5	9	3.1	34.444
		g	28	7.8	27.86	21	6.1	29.05	17	4.8	28.235	8	2.1	26.25	7	3.4	48.571
	Folded grip	b	-12	2.2	-18.33	-11	2	-18.18	-12	2.1	-17.5	-4	1.8	-45	-5	2	-40
	135 ⁰	g	-18	2.4	-13.33	-14	2.1	-15	-13	2	-15.38	-3	1.9	-63.33	-3	1.8	-60

The large values of the coefficient of variation are explained by the low values of the maximum indicators. The problem here is that the small absolute error has a high relative weight. On the other hand, the

assessment of the absolute errors is also compromised, since low maxima generally do not allow for high absolute levels.

Table 3.

Correlation coefficient between test and retest data

years old		3 years	4 years	5 years	6 years	7 years
r-test	b	0,27	0,32	0,64	0,89	0,92
retest	g	0,12	0,21	0,66	0,79	0,92

However, we believe that this new type of information reflects essential parameters of the control system. The behavior of the correlation coefficient between the test and retest data is interesting (see Table

3). The highest gradient is observed between 4 and 5 years. Without having the necessary evidence, it could be assumed that at the expense of quantitative changes during this time interval, a qualitative restructuring in

the control of the motor apparatus takes place. The results obtained also indicate that these tests are reliable for children over 4 years old.

Conclusions

➤ The conclusions of the development point to the idea of rethinking the methods and means for assessing the ability to accurately reproduce muscular effort and the ability to internally readjust compensatory mechanisms.

➤ The low correlation coefficients are striking, which is an indication that the educational process should provide for targeted methods and means for educating management in view of the mutual connection and conditionality between the kinematic and dynamic structures.

➤ Generally accepted tests for assessing physical ability are not always directly applicable to preschool children. The main reasons are two: the high weight of the technical component on the result and the variability of psychological factors. Therefore, it is necessary to refine the motor tasks so that they represent an age-appropriate problem for the motor system.

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